

The Influence of English Teacher Certification and Non-Certification towards the Students' Understanding on English Grammar at SMAN 4 Halmahera Barat and at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate

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Abstract

This research used a comparative causal design which was contained test and interview. The objectives of this research are to know could the Teacher certification and non-certification Influence the students understanding on English grammar and to know what problems did the students find when they study English grammar by the Teacher certification and non-certification at that school. The data were collected by using test and interview for the students of that schools. The sample of this research at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR was 22 students and at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate was 21 students of the tenth grade both of the schools. By using grammar material to students who are taught by certified and non-certified teachers in these two schools, namely in SMAN 3 Kota Ternate and at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR the researcher have taken the results of the student evaluation test provided by the two teachers to be able to determine the results of the two schools before being combined with the results of the interview. From the results of this study show that the results of the evaluation of students at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate and combined with the results of the interview, are better than the results of evaluation and interview at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR. In this research, the researcher given conclude to us that the result of teaching grammar through teacher certification at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate is better than students' result at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR by the teacher of non-certification.

Keywords: teacher certification, English grammar, ex-post facto research design, test, interview, quantitative research method.

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1. Background

English is used by many people in the world for different purposes such as to communicate to other people from different countries and provide a means for exchanging knowledge. It is in line to Richard (2007:2) who states that English is the language of globalization, international communication, and commerce and trade media. So it is important for people to learn English, because English is used in every aspect of the society life, in this study the researcher will try to know how the teacher who certified and non-certified teach for the students about English especially English Grammar at senior high school at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR and at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate.

Teacher certification leaves a great deal of room for varied meaning. It can mean alternative ways to meet teachers certification requirements such as graduate level masters' degree program rather than an undergraduate teacher education program. It can mean alternative standards for certification which allows for truncated or reduced training or for training completed during the course of teaching career rather than prior to its initiation. Or it can mean alternatives to state certification itself, as where a state allows local employers to train and certify their own candidates. (*Brouns, Journal of Teacher Education, September 2001*).

Teacher non-certification in education is complex work involving curriculum, pedagogy and research, yet most teacher educators are provided with little professional development support or mentoring in most teacher education programs. On the one hand, we are expected to attend to, and experiment with, clinical aspects of practice as teacher educators in order to develop into skilled practitioners. At the same time, the academy expects teacher educators to pursue rigorous programs of research. While most teacher educators begin with a deep commitment to effective teaching and pedagogical reform, the culture of education colleges and the promotion criteria and other reward systems within universities privileges scholarship over clinical practice. Overcoming these barriers is “a constant source of tension, frustration, and challenge” . (Gallagher, Griffin, Parker, Kitchen, & Figg, 2011:880).

Specifically, this research wants to find out whether there are any qualities in teaching process between teacher certification and non-certification about the students understanding on English grammar at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR and at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate where the teacher certification and non-certification teaches.

Researcher wants to know about the quality of teacher certification and non-certification to influence the students understanding Specifically on English grammar at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR and SMAN 3 Kota Ternate Some of the theory suggest that grammar teaching can be put aside of the lexical approach to improve the students understand on English language (Lewis, 1993:148).

Study grammar is very important to achieve the student knowledge of English language itself “Reference to the mechanism according to which language works when it is used to communicate with other people. Grammar is a mechanism for putting words together, but we have said little about sound of meaning.”(Leech, 1982:3).

Grammar also can improve our language skill especially in communication with the other people not only that, grammar also could make easy to study English language (Swan, 2005), The rules that show how words are combined, arranged or changed to show certain kinds of meaning.

Teacher certification has qualities like definition above to make students understand about the materials. In this research focus to influence teacher certification and non-certification towards the students understanding on English grammar. However, when it comes to the first grades at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR and at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate based on the writer's test at the school some students have limited their structure to make a sentence. It means the students and the teacher certification and non-certification have problems in teaching and study process. so that's why the researcher comes to the school to know what extent senior high school teachers has applied skills teaching after passing the certification examination and how to teaches to students about grammar and has a different with the teacher non-certification about the result of the student understanding on English grammar. In addition, this research has the aim to find out the problems that the teachers have in their application of skills teaching. Based on the problems, this research proposes some recommendations for the solutions of the problems about how should the teacher certification and non-certification teaches and how should the students study about grammar.

In this research the researcher focuses to know the influence of teacher certification and non-certification towards the students understanding on English grammar, especially the researcher wants to know that teacher certification can make students to understand about grammar then the teacher non-certification if not what the problem it all. Does it because of the students or the teacher certification and non-certification itself? In this research the research tries to find out what the problem and how to solve the problem itself.

2. Theoretical Basis

2.1 Teacher Certification

Teaching is an especially demanding, yet particularly rewarding profession. Few careers ask so much of a person's character and creativity, and few professions give as much satisfaction in return. Teacher certification is a teacher provides professional opportunities for teaching in public, parochial, and private schools (Diane S. Brown, Ph.D., IHM 1983-1992).

International Teacher Certified can helps teachers to develop their skills, understanding and deepen their knowledge around the intersection of intercultural awareness and global competence empowering them not only to support students in becoming global change makers, but to serve as catalyst of school-wide culture change, as well (<https://www.ecis.org/learning/itc>).

2.2 Non-Certification

“Teacher non-certified from in education is complex work involving curriculum, pedagogy and research, yet most teacher educators are provided with little professional development support or

mentoring in most teacher education programs to can make improve their skills in learning process to be good teacher” (Gallagher, Griffin, Parker, Kitchen, & Figg, 2011:880).

2.3. Grammar

Grammar is concerned with language in general rather than with an individual language, as is the study of essential components of any human language, transformational grammar is one variety of theoretical grammar (Richard Nordquist (2002)).

Grammar or syntax is concerned with making completely explicit the formalisms of grammar, and in providing scientific arguments or explanations in favour of one account of grammar rather than another, in terms of a general theory of human language.

“Theories of grammar, grammatical analyses, and grammatical statements may be divided into three types: structural formal, and functional. Structural grammar describes such grammatical structures as phonemes, morphemes, syntactic relations, semantics, inter clause relations, constituents, dependencies, sentences, and occasionally, as with tagmemics and glossematics, texts an discourse”. (Nichols, 1984).

Understanding and using English grammar is contain changes directed primarily toward clarification of structure presentations in the charts and improvements in the exercises (Azar, 1989).

Teacher Certification Degrees is a comprehensive guide for individuals who want to learn how to become a teacher or further their teaching career by earning an advanced degree. We feature expert written content to help you learn the essential information for teaching certification in your state. If you are researching school options in your state, you will find profiles of popular schools and reviews of teacher certification programs by former students by clicking on your state in the list below. Learn what it takes to be successful in the classroom by visiting our career interview section which shares insights and advice from our interviews with over 50 current teachers from across the country. You can also find the latest job openings for teachers in your state on our teaching jobs board that is updated daily. (*Martin 1959 Teacher Certification of Teachers of English*).

The certification process is a capability testing process and one of the abilities tested is grammar in order to have a standard of ability or expertise in the field, especially to the English language certification teacher, so as to produce teacher candidates who have the competence in planning, implementing, assessing learning, follow up the results of the assessment, do the guidance and training of students, and conduct research, and be able to develop professionalism in a sustainable manner and also master the teacher's competence as a whole in accordance with national education standards (Minister of National Education Regulation No. 8 of 2009 concerning PPG).

3. Method

This study use quantitative method. This study focuses on the influence of teacher certification and non-certification to students' understanding on English grammar at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR and at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate.

Quantitative methods is emphasize objective measurements and the statistical, mathematical, or numerical analysis of data collected through polls, questionnaires, and surveys, or by manipulating pre-existing statistical data using computational techniques. Quantitative research focuses on gathering numerical data and generalizing it across groups of people or to explain a particular phenomenon. Babbie, Earl R. (2010).

The researcher chooses test and interview to find out the teacher certification and non-certification result of teaching for the student of English grammar. the test consist of ten questions to the students about the understanding on English grammar by the teacher certification and non-certification and around ten question to the interview for the student about the teacher certification and non-certification.

In this research the researcher took the quantitative method designs have a purpose to identify the influence of teacher certification and non-certification about the students understanding on English grammar.

The research design employed is comparative causal or ex-post facto to identify the problem in this research of the teacher certification and non-certification about the influence of student understanding on English grammar.

A correlation study involves the collection two or more sets of data from a group of subjects with the attempt to determine the subsequent relationship between those sets of data (Tuckman, 1978:147). This type of approach might be diagramed as follows:

$$O_1 O_2$$

1. the variable that O_1 is measuring has caused O_2 (as the experimenter has suggested)
2. the variable that O_2 is measuring has caused O_1 ;
3. some third, unmeasured, variable has caused both O_1 and O_2

Population is all the individuals or units of interest; typically, there is not available data for almost all individuals in a population (Bret Hanlon and Bret Larget September 2011). Population in this research is all students at SMA N 4 HAL-BAR and at SMAN and at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate especially

XI IPA at the school itself. At SMAN 4 HAL-BAR there are consists to 45 students and at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate there are consist to 50 students.

The research took place at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR and SMAN 3 Kota Ternate because the ordered of university and the researcher has a good relationship with head of the school. It will help him to cope with the school regulation in doing research then the influence of the teacher certification and non-certification to the student is a subject of this research and English grammar is one of the material that were required.

In this research the researcher will take the sample at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR especially class of XI IPA 1 the students consist to 22 students and the second at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate the students there are consist to 21 students.

Sample is a subset of the individuals in a population; there is typically data available for individuals in samples (Bret Hanlon and Bret Larget September 8, 2011).

From the data collection to answer the following research questions, in this study the researcher provide procedure or technic of data collection there are consist to students' test for measure the students' understanding about English grammar by the teacher who certified and non-certified and the interview to know what are problems when they study grammar from the teacher who certified and from the teacher non-certified.

In this section the data analysis of what have been gathered from the students, data analysis was conducted after the data collection. In order to catch the valid data, this research adopted da ta collection method including students' test and interview.

4. Finding and Discussion

4.1 The result of the Test

This study was conducted in two activities, there are consist to:

1. Test
2. Interview

The first in this study, the researcher made a test for the students to found result, how far the students understanding on grammar at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR and at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate. The last in this study the researcher tried to interview the problem of students at that school.

“Analysis means the categorizing, ordering, manipulating and the last for summarizing of the data obtain answer for the research Question” (Kerlinger,1988). Based on the notions the writer applied data analysis as the purpose of analysis is to deduce data to be intelligible and interpretable so the relation of the research problem can be studied.

In a test activities, the teacher did written test (multiple-choice) in order to collect the students result. The teacher certification and non-certification provided a simple Question of grammar for the students.

4.1.1 The result test at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR

After the researcher taken a result test of students at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR to know how well the students understanding on English grammar by the teacher non-certification can be seen in the table below:

SMAN 4 Halmahera Barat

No	Name	Questions							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	Total	Result %
1	ML	1	1	0	1	1	0	4	66
2	SNRH	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	STM	1	1	0	1	1	0	4	66
4	AL	1	1	0	0	0	0	2	33
5	JWD	1	1	0	1	1	0	4	66
6	LK.K	0	0	0	1	0	1	2	33
7	RR.G	0	1	1	0	0	1	3	50
8	GR	0	0	1	0	0	1	2	33
9	IIS	1	1	0	1	1	0	4	66
10	SL	0	0	0	1	1	1	3	50
11	MN.H	1	0	0	0	0	1	2	33
12	RF	1	1	0	1	1	0	4	66
13	AYK	1	1	0	1	1	0	4	66
14	MK	1	1	1	1	1	0	5	83
15	DG	0	0	1	1	0	0	2	33
16	AD	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	16
17	JDM	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	16
18	GMPT	1	1	0	1	1	0	4	66
19	SP	0	1	1	0	0	0	2	33
20	CG	0	1	1	1	0	1	4	66
21	EM	1	1	1	0	0	0	3	50
22	YS	0	1	0	1	0	0	2	33

	TOTAL	13	14	7	13	9	6		
Percentage Average									46.55%

The average of the students result score = 46.55%

From the analysis above, it is showed the higher score from the result test of the students at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR is 83 (Eighty three) and the middle is 66 (Sixty six) and last the lower score is 0 (zero).

Level Score

High Score	Middle Score	Low Score
83	66	0

From the results of the grammar test evaluation that was taught by non-certified teachers at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR out of a total of 22 students with 6 questions the overall student average outcome of the 100% target was only 46.55% they achieved. then the next researcher will try to see the results or the average value obtained by students from SMAN 3 Kota ternate so that researchers can conclude which school has a high average value than at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR is taught by teachers who do not certified or at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate which is taught by a certified teacher it will be help the researchers to find out did the teachers certification can influence Grammar students than the teachers who have not certified or not.

4.1.2 Result test at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate

After the researcher finished analyzing the evaluation test result about grammar that was taught by teacher who has not certified at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR, then the researcher sees the result of the student evaluation test which is taught by the teacher who has been certified at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate.)

The data of the students result test score at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate can be seen in the table.

SMAN 3 Kota Ternate

No	Name	Questions						
		1	2	3	4	5	Total	Result %
1	A	1	1	0	1	0	3	60
2	S I	1	1	0	1	0	3	60
3	H Y M	1	1	1	1	0	4	80
4	S I	1	1	1	1	0	4	80
5	M A R	1	1	0	0	0	2	40
6	Z M A	0	1	1	0	1	3	60
7	G G	0	1	1	0	1	3	60
8	A Y	1	0	0	0	1	2	40
9	A K	1	1	0	0	1	3	60
10	I B	1	0	0	0	1	2	40
11	R R	1	1	1	0	1	4	80
12	N A A.R H	1	1	1	0	1	4	80
13	D M P R	1	0	1	1	0	3	60
14	S M A. F	1	0	0	1	0	2	40
15	E M	1	0	1	1	0	3	60
16	F S	1	1	0	0	1	3	60
17	F A	1	1	1	0	1	4	80
18	J H	1	0	1	1	0	3	60
19	N I M. W	1	0	1	1	0	3	60
20	F M K	0	0	0	0	1	1	20
21	S	1	1	1	1	1	5	100
	TOTAL	18	13	12	10	11		
Percentage Average								60.95%

The average of the students result score = 60.95%

From the analysis above, it is showed the higher score from the result test of the students at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate is 100 (One hundred) and the middle score is 88 (Eighty Eight) and last the lower score is 20 (Twenty).

Level Score

High Score	Middle Score	Low Score
100	80	20

4.1.3 The interview interpretation

Besides conducting an evaluation test, the researcher has also conducted an interview. which aims to know about the understanding and also the performance of certified teachers and teachers who have not been certified about the teaching and learning process of grammar materials to students of class X at two schools namely in SMAN 3 Kota Ternate and at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR.

The research provide the interview using Indonesian language. There were five (5) Questions. The Question number one about student problems in the learning process and questions 2, 3 and 4 about students' understanding and question number 5 regarding learning time.

The result of interview for the students at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR and SMAN 3 Kota Ternate are as follows:

1. The number of sample at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR: 22 students (the tenth class at senior high school).
2. The number of sample at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate: 21 students (the tenth class at senior high school).
3. The number of item: 5 items (five Questions).

a). For the Question number (1): Constraints in the learning process

In this Questions number 1 about the constraints in the learning process who though by the teacher certified and non-certified let is to see:

Student (Q1): In this case after the researchers analyzed the results of the interview test students from both schools in North Maluku. At SMAN 4 HAL-BAR with a total sample size of 22 and only 10 of their total sample said that they have no constraints during the teaching and learning process (Q1 S4): There are no obstacles that I get in the learning process. Unlike with SMAN 3 Kota Ternate with a total sample of 21 and 15 of the total sample said that there are no obstacles when the learning process takes place (Q1 S5: I do not have a problem because the teacher skill is good).

From the data above about the problems students of learning process by teacher certification and non-certification can showed to us about the different result by students at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR though by the teacher non-certification from total 22 just 10 students answered constraints in the learning process but at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate though by the teacher certification from total 21 and 15 students answered constraints in learning process so the researchers can conclude that schools with better teacher certification are compared with schools with uncertified teachers.

b). For the Question number (2): The teacher skills

For the Questions number 2 of the teacher certified and non-certified skills to know who the teacher is influence the students understanding of the grammar materials at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate and at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR.

Students (Q2): Concerning the problem of this question the researcher has analyzed the results of the interviews of all students with the results at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR with a total sample size of 22 students and only 8 students who said that liked the way of teaching. Then in SMAN 3 Kota Ternate with total sample of 21 students and 19 students said that like the way of teaching.

From the result case above about the skills of the teacher certification and non-certification in teaching process the research can be concluded also that skills of certified teacher is better than teacher non-certified.

c). For the Question number (3): The understanding of the materials

From the Question number 3 to the students about the understanding of the grammar materials who though by the teacher certified and non-certified

Students (Q3): From the result of the interview analysis from all students at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR with the total of 22 students from the total there just 5 students said that understand about the material taught by the teacher (Q3 S4: yes easy to understand the materials) and at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate with total sample total 21 and 14 students said that they very understood of the material taught by the teacher (Q3 S13: yes I like and teacher skill is fun).

The data above it shows to us that the results of certified teacher about the students understanding of the materials is very improved the students than teachers who have not-certified.

d). For the Question number (4): The interesting of the materials

The Questions number 4 about the interesting students of the materials of grammar who though by the teacher certified and non-certified namely at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate and at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR.

From the evaluation result the researcher has analyzed the interview result from the two schools concerned where the SMAN 4 HAL-BAR with the total number of samples as 22 and 22 also the students said that like the material in teaching (Q4 S6: yes I like because I really want to know to English language) is not different with school at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate from the total sample as 21 all of them said that like with the material taught about the grammar (Q4 S3: when the teacher though is very fun).

From the data above about the interesting of the materials grammar by the teacher certified and teacher non-certified they are same it means that students from both schools like with grammar material.

e). For the Question number (5): Teacher teaching time

From the Question number 5 the researcher has taken the data of the students answered by the students interview result about the teacher teaching time from the teacher certification and non-certification at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate and SMAN 4 HAL-BAR.

Students (Q5): After the researchers analyzed the interview results from the two schools from SMAN 4 HAL-BAR with a total of 22 samples all of them said that the teacher concerned always came on time in the learning process as well and also at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate of a total of 21 overall also said the that the teacher always comes on time.

The case from data above about the teacher teaching time by the teacher certified and non-certified at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate and at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR they are same always consistent came to the school for teach.

4.1.4 Discussion

Takes the result of analysis, make the interference pertinent of the research relation studied and draws conclusions about these relations

(Kelinger,1988:126).

From the result of evaluation test at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR with average value from result of students from 21 students with 6 questions from target 100% only reach 45.55% but at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate with achievement of mean value from students result with 5 questions from 100% target they reach 60.95% achievement.

From the second result of the evaluation test, the researcher can conclude that the students of class X are special subjects in English that are taught by teachers who have not certified at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR with the average result value from the students who follow the evaluation result test with the

number of questions 6 items in the form of multiple choice with grammar material from the target 100% can only reach 45.55% while at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate with the same class, the same subjects and also the same material about grammar with the number of questions 5 grains in the form multiple choice but taught by certified teachers of 100% target can reach 60.95%.

It means that the result of the average value of the two schools SMAN 3 Kota Ternate with achievement 60.90% higher than the result of the average value of students at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR with only reach 45.95%. it shows that student evaluation result at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate with teacher certified higher than result of student evaluation at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR by teacher which not yet certified.

Certified Teacher	Non-certified Teacher	Differences
60.95%	46.55%	14.4%

5. Conclusion

In the previous chapter the research had analyzed the data of the result test and supporting by the students result of interview. The result of SMAN 4 HAL-BAR 46.55% who though by the teacher non-certified and at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate with the score 60.95% who though by the teacher certified the different is 1.32%. So the research can conclude that the students at SMAN 3 Kota Ternate who though by the teacher certified can influence their understanding on English grammar than the students at SMAN 4 HAL-BAR who though by the teacher non-certified.

After finishing the analysis, the researcher can conclude some other effects of the students who though by the teacher certified and non-certified there are:

1. The teacher who certified has good influence for the students' English grammar skills.
2. Study grammar with the teacher who certified can influence the students understanding on English grammar than the teacher non-certified.
3. Teaching English grammar by teacher non-certified students still have a problem about vocabulary.
4. Learning study through the teacher who certified gave more chance to students for understanding about grammar rather than the teacher non-certified

5. Learn English grammar by the teacher non-certified have a problem because some of them said that difficult to make a sentence.
6. Studied English grammar by the teacher non-certified students sometimes boring in learning process.

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